

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY OF MASTERPIECES OF WORLD LITERATURE “WAR AND PEACE” BY LEO TOLSTOY

Ma'murjonova Madinaxon Ulug'bekovna,

1st year student of UzSWLU, group 2408

E-mail: madinaxonmamurjonovs@gmail.com

Scientific adviser: Jumakulova Nargiza

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Annotation. *War and piece is a well known 19th century Russian novel , written and published by author Leo Tolstoy between 1867 and 1869 years. This article explores the research methodologies and analytical approaches applied to Leo Tolstoy's novel War and piece as a masterpiece of world literature. It examines the novel's historical, literary significance emphasizing Tolstoy's unique narrative techniques , character development and use of realism. The novel originally written in Russia, consists of four books and an epilogue with over 559 characters and 365 chapters making it one of the most ambitious works in literary history.*

Key words: *War, peace, classical literature, Russia, French, literary, characters.*

Introduction. The book was Initially written in Russian and consists of four parts (or books) along with an epilogue divided into two sections. The novel has 1225 pages, 559 characters and 365 chapters. The story focuses on Napoleon's invasion of Russia in 1812 and follows three main characters. It revolves around three central figures in literature: Natasha Rostova, Prince Andrei Bolkonsky, and Pierre Bezukhov. The novel examines significant historical events through the lives of real, socially engaged individuals. It is known for its complex and richly developed characters, making it one of the greatest works in world literature. Novel explores various themes such as struggle and love , society and wealth , finding a good balance between the chaos of war and the peace of everyday live. Perhaps this must be the greatest of the world's fictional works. Tolstoy's masterful storytelling combined with his ability to portray deep psychological complexity makes War and peace one of the most influential works in world literature. However this novel also known for its length and complexity. Before reading the novel readers may feel lazy some may feel even bored because it requires time , effort and concentration.

Literature review. Lev Tolstoy was a Russian writer, dramatist, novelist, and philosopher, famous for his epic novels and lengthy works such as War and Peace and Anna Karenina. He was born into an aristocratic Russian family on September 9, 1828. Recognized as a master of realistic fiction, Tolstoy is regarded as one of the

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world's greatest novelists. Tolstoy's literary works are known for their psychological depth, intricate character development, and detailed depictions of Russian society. Readers have long admired his ability to create "absolute language"—a style that, despite its potential to weaken realism, remains aesthetically powerful in his hands. The 19th-century British poet and critic Matthew Arnold once remarked that a novel by Tolstoy is not just a work of art but "a piece of life." Similarly, the Russian author Isaak Babel famously stated, "If the world could write by itself, it would write like Tolstoy.

Research methodology. War and Peace begins in the Russian city of St. Petersburg in 1805, as fear of Napoleon's ongoing war making begins to set in. Most of the characters are introduced at a party, including Pierre Bezukhov, Andrey Bolkonsky, and the Kuragin and Rostov families. Much of the novel focuses on the interactions between the Bezukhoffs, Bolkonskys, and the Rostovs. After their introduction, Andrey Bolkonsky and Nikolay Rostov go to the Austrian front under General Kutuzov, a fictional representation of Mikhail Kutuzov, to engage with Napoleon's troops. Andrey is then injured at the Battle of Austerlitz and presumed dead, until he arrives home to his wife, Lise, who dies during childbirth soon after. Pierre, meanwhile, has married Helene Kuragina. She is unfaithful to him, and Pierre duels with the other man, almost killing him. He soon becomes overwhelmed by his marriage and leaves Helene. He joins the Freemasons, which influences his personal and business fortunes greatly. In the meantime Nikolay has racked up a large amount of gambling debt, which causes the Rostov family to lose most of their fortune. He is encouraged to marry a wealthy heiress, despite promising to marry Sonya, his cousin. Nikolay eventually witnesses the peace between Tsar Alexander I and Napoleon (Treaties of Tilsit, signed in 1807). Andrey soon becomes involved with Natasha Rostov only to be told by his father that he must wait a year before marrying her. After some time away, Andrey discovers that Natasha has been unfaithful. He rejects her, and Pierre consoles her, eventually falling in love with her. In 1812 Napoleon invades Russia, forcing Alexander to declare war. Andrey returns to service, and Pierre is driven to believe he must personally assassinate Napoleon. As the French advance, Mary, Andrey's sister, is forced to leave her house. Nikolay finds her

in the streets, and the two reconnect. Pierre, still crazed by his imaginary duty, is apprehended by French forces and witnesses a number of executions, which deeply affect him. During his imprisonment, he befriends Platon Karatev, a wise peasant. He is later freed from the French and promptly falls ill. After recovering, he marries

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Natasha, and they have four children together. Nikolay weds Mary, and the two enjoy a happy married life.

When reading *War and Peace*, you will often come across beautiful and quotable sentences. Tolstoy frequently uses sharp and detailed comparisons, making the scenes feel almost cinematic—just like watching a movie. His dialogues are powerful, though some parts of the novel feature repetition, adding to the novel's immersive realism. Despite its length and depth, Tolstoy's writing remains accessible, even for readers new to classic literature. Tolstoy was instrumental in bringing a new kind of consciousness to the novel. His narrative structure is noted not only for its god's-eye point of view over and within events, but also in the way it swiftly and seamlessly portrayed an individual character's viewpoint. His use of visual detail is often comparable to cinema, using literary techniques that resemble panning, wide shots, and close-ups. These devices, while not exclusive to Tolstoy, are part of the new style of the novel that arose in the mid-19th century and of which Tolstoy proved himself a master. The standard Russian text of *War and Peace* is divided into four volumes, comprising fifteen books, and an epilogue split into two parts. Roughly the first half is concerned strictly with the fictional characters, whereas the latter parts, as well as the second part of the epilogue, increasingly consist of essays about the nature of war, power, history, and historiography. Tolstoy interspersed these essays into the story in a way that defies previous fictional convention. Certain abridged versions remove these essays entirely, while others, published even during Tolstoy's life, simply moved these essays into an appendix.

The essays in *War and Peace*, which begin in the second half of the book, satirize all attempts to formulate general laws of history and reject the ill-considered assumptions supporting all historical narratives. In Tolstoy's view, history, like battle, is essentially the product of contingency, has no direction, and fits no pattern. The causes of historical events are infinitely varied and forever unknowable, and so historical writing, which claims to explain the past, necessarily falsifies it. The shape of historical narratives reflects not the actual course of events but the essentially literary criteria established by earlier historical narratives.

In the second half of *War and Peace*, Tolstoy includes a series of philosophical essays that challenge traditional historical narratives. He criticizes the idea that history follows a predictable pattern or is shaped by the intentions of great leaders. Instead, he argues that historical events result from countless small, unpredictable decisions made by ordinary people. Tolstoy rejects the notion that history is driven by major political figures or military strategists, believing instead that true historical

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change is the result of everyday actions. He compares historians' view of history to someone looking at a landscape from afar and seeing only the treetops—missing the millions of individual details that make up the whole. Because of this perspective, *War and Peace* includes numerous small incidents, each contributing in a subtle way to the broader historical picture. This approach sets Tolstoy apart from the intellectuals of his time, making his philosophy of history one of the most debated aspects of his work. His belief in the power of the ordinary and his skepticism toward grand historical theories remain influential and through provoking to this day.

The accolades for Leo Tolstoy's *War and Peace* from notable literary figures were published in various letters, articles, and reviews: Ivan Turgenev: Initially skeptical, Turgenev later acknowledged the novel's significance. In his 1880 article addressed to Edmond About, editor of the French newspaper *Le XIX^e Siècle*, he described *War and Peace* as "one of the most remarkable books of our age," praising its epic spirit and original narrative style Virginia Woolf: Upon finishing the novel, Woolf declared Tolstoy "the greatest of all novelists," reflecting her profound appreciation for his literary genius. These accolades highlight the widespread recognition of *War and Peace* as a monumental work in world literature.

In *War and peace* Leo Tolstoy presents three whose lives during the Napoleonic periods: Pierre Bezukhov

The large-bodied, ungainly, and socially awkward illegitimate son of an old Russian grandee. Pierre, educated abroad, returns to Russia as a misfit. His unexpected inheritance of a large fortune makes him socially desirable. Pierre is ensnared by the fortune-hunting Helene Kuragina, whose eventual deception leaves him depressed and confused, spurring a spiritual odyssey that spans the novel. Pierre eventually marries Natasha Rostova.

Andrew Bolkonski

The intelligent, disciplined, and ambitious son of the retired military commander Prince Bolkonski. Andrew is coldly analytical and resistant to flights of emotion. Lonely after the death of his wife, Lise, he falls in love with Natasha, but is unable to forgive her momentary passion for Anatole.

Natasha Rostova

The lively and irrepressible daughter of the Rostov family, who charms everyone she meets. Natasha falls in love with a series of men and then becomes seriously committed to Andrew, though she ruins the relationship by engaging in a brief tryst with Anatole Kuragin. Eventually, Natasha marries Pierre and becomes a stout, unkempt matron.

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Conclusion. Leo Tolstoy's *War and Peace* stands as one of the greatest works of world literature, offering a rich blend of historical narrative, philosophical inquiry, and deeply developed characters. Through the lives of Pierre Bezukhov, Prince Andrei Bolkonsky, and Natasha Rostova, Tolstoy explores love, ambition, war, and human resilience, making the novel not just a historical epic but also a profound study of human nature.

Tolstoy's writing style, known for its cinematic detail, psychological depth, and seamless shifts in perspective, revolutionized literature and influenced generations of writers. His philosophy of history, expressed in the novel's later essays, challenges traditional historical narratives by emphasizing the power of ordinary people's actions over the so-called great leaders.

Despite its length and complexity, *War and Peace* remains a timeless and rewarding read, offering valuable lessons on life, fate, and the interconnectedness of human experiences. Its impact on literature, history, and philosophy ensures that it will continue to be studied and appreciated for generations to come.

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